

IMPROVE UPPER GRADES' SPEAKING SKILL WITH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Nowadays teachers and educators widely discuss the necessity of reviewing and updating the pedagogies used all over the globe. Though the increasing number of schools is reported to be innovating, schools remain largely seen as very resistant places for innovation. That is why, it is important to underline that the so-called “joy of teaching” and “joy of learning” combined are the key principles in creating positive educational environment. Thus, child-centered and learner-friendly educational environment is becoming a great priority as interactive methodologies make learning enjoyable and exciting to students and improve their retention, participation and performance. Interactive methods help teachers to encourage greater attentiveness, interest and responsiveness in children while improving their language skills. Developing young learners’ speaking skills deals with boosting their verbal and thinking capacity and interest to language and cultural diversity. The effectiveness of teaching young learners correlates with a teacher’s ability to resort to various strategies among which interactive cognitive strategies prevail since they provide proper acquisition of speaking skills. The major principle of teaching speaking proves to be improvement of young learners’ listening and speaking skills to be involved in the process of communication. It should be noted that a teacher working with children deal with so-called mixed-ability groups. That is why a teacher has to take into consideration multiple intelligences of students: different types of personality,

thinking, scope of attention, the ability to perceive and process information. Apparently, teaching young learners requires special approaches to planning and organizing the educational process. Experts highlight meaningful practice which suggests an activity where language control is still provided but where students are required to make meaningful choices when carrying out practice. Buhrow and Garcia recognize, that meaningful practice results in meaningful communication, because for kids, learning is all about exploring their passions and interests. In this respect, we believe interactive methods (IMs) to be one of the most effective tools. It helps to create comfortable educational environment, smooth psychological barriers and it results in stimulating young learners' activities. In the framework of IMs, students are encouraged by the teacher to search for information independently, to interact with readiness and enthusiasm in communicative situations. To promote students' communicative competence and to make lessons more purposeful and interactive such activities as simulation and role-play are to be employed as they contribute to students' considering themselves as much real as possible. Foreign language teachers should be accurate in designing learner-friendly, supportive and nurturing educational environment and help pupils become confident and enthusiastic communicators. Teaching young learners is always a challenge and requires new sophisticated approaches and solutions in terms of developing speaking skills. A more student friendly educational environment is to be created to provide efficiency and boost kids' motivation in learning foreign languages. Furthermore, brainstorming proved to be very resultative. On the one hand, it meets kids' desire to play, on the second hand, it provokes their creative thinking and expands their active vocabulary. The experiment showed that Talking timebomb turned to be their favourite among both teachers and students as it practically needs no time to prepare for it. The teacher suggests a topic, then he/she switches on some piece of music and gives them a ball. The kid who has the ball says one word on the topic and passes the ball another one. Thus, they revise the vocabulary, and when the music stops, the student with the ball loses the game and gets the "punishment". It means he/she has to speak at least 30 seconds on the topic. It

should be mentioned that this activity can be used to revise not only active vocabulary but speech patterns or grammar constructions. The reflexive stage plays no less crucial role in developing speaking skills. The teacher summarizes the aims reached during the lesson, giving the students opportunity to share their impressions on activities (games, puzzles, brainstorming, etc.). It is important to highlight that students' comments, ideas, or criticism should not be ignored by planning the following lesson. But it doesn't mean that the teacher changes the structure of a lesson, on the contrary, he/she tries to be more flexible and uses activities which facilitate learning process and boost students' motivation and creativity. The segments of the pie chart show percentage and three levels of the kids' speaking skills. The vast majority of young learners face serious difficulties in speaking.

Conclusion

Teachers should be ready to prepare learner-friendly lessons with thematic approaches for more holistic learning. While planning and organizing a lesson, a teacher should keep in mind some key principles, which help to make young learners' teaching speaking more resultative:

- language immersion;
- young learner friendly educational environment;
- awareness of different types of personality and psychological peculiarities;
- kids' interaction and communication in class;
- delicate mistakes correction and proper encouragement.

The study has shown that interactive methods prove to be one of the most effective tools in developing young learners' speaking skills.

References:

1. Ahmed, S. T. S., & Pawar, S. V. (2018). Communicative competence in English as a foreign language: Its meaning and the pedagogical considerations for its development. *The Creative Launcher*, 2(4), 301-312.

2. Becker, C., & Roos, J. (2016). An approach to creative speaking activities in the young learners' classroom. *Education Inquiry*, 7(1), 27613.
 3. Buhrow, B., & Garcia, A. U. (2006). *Ladybugs, Tornadoes, and Swirling Galaxies: English Language Learners Discover Their World Through Inquiry*. Portsmouth, NH: Stenhouse Publishers.
 4. B.Kh. Khodjayev, *Theory and practice of general pedagogy T - 2017*.
 5. O.U.Avlayev, S.Jo'rayea, S.P.Mirzayeva, "Educational methods" instruction manual, "Navroz" publishing house, Tashkent – 2017.
 6. Sodikova, B. I., Bobojonov, D. J. O. G. L., & Abdumalikov, F. B. O. G. L. (2021). Language and relations between speech activity. *Science and Education*, 2(12), 641-645.
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